
CSCW as an engaged program. Notes on public cooperative practices and critical theory

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Abstract

With this paper we would like to join the conversation around CSCW and social theory by reflecting upon the role of contemporary critical theory in further expanding CSCW research, both theoretically and empirically. Our arguments are based on the development of an EU-funded project, called PIE News¹, which aims to design a digital platform to help contrasting conditions of poverty, lack of income and unemployment in Europe. The intellectual background of the project draws upon contemporary critical theory, Autonomous

Marxism in particular. In claiming that theories make reality, not only describe it, we discuss how critical theory and forms of contemporary participatory design can be aligned in the light of contemporary digital capitalism. We outline a few questions for CSCW, showing how the achievements of the field so far can benefit from a renewed attention to political economy, in order to fit in the current social context in a progressive way.

Author Keywords

Computer-supported cooperative work; Public design; critical theory; Autonomous Marxism

Introduction

In 2000, Computer-Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW) made its debut in a renowned sociological arena, such as the British Journal of Sociology, through a special issue dedicated to the emergence of 'workplace studies' [10]. In the introductory piece, Christian Heath and Graham Button [11] regards 'workplace studies' as a relatively unknown research field within sociology, and more attuned to concepts, ideas, debates and developments in areas such as CSCW and HCI (Human-Computer Interaction). In saying so, Heath and Button clearly identified an

1 <http://pieproject.eu>

intellectual divide between CSCW and social theory until then, while suggesting a common ground between a number of issues in the study of cooperative work practices and contemporary debates within sociology.

The juxtaposition of workplace studies and CSCW is meaningful inasmuch as it clarifies the central focus around which empirical and theoretical research in CSCW has been developed, that is to say the workplace practices and the ways in which tools and technologies feature in work and collaboration. As a matter of fact, Kjeld Schmidt describes CSCW as arising “from the organization of modern work, from the incessant attempts to make the coordination of interdependent activities more efficient, reliable, flexible, etc. by means of computational artifacts” [17, p.413].

However, CSCW as research program did not develop in a vacuum as Schmidt himself and Bannon point out [18], but a range of conceptual frameworks originating in other research areas — distributed computing, software engineering, organization theory, industrial sociology, sociology of science, information systems design, psychology of learning, activity theory, distributed cognition, social psychology and other — were imported as researchers from these areas became engaged in CSCW.

Such disciplinary contamination has prompted a heterogeneous body of research, grappling with typical CSCW-related notions — such as ‘situated action’, ‘articulation work’, ‘distributed cognition’, ‘activity systems’ — articulated in sundry empirical settings. Starting from these considerations, in this paper we would like to reflect upon the role of contemporary

critical theory in further expanding and enriching CSCW research, both theoretically and empirically.

Our arguments are based on the development on an EU-funded project, called PIE News², which aims to design a digital platform that will supplement the existing public measures contrasting conditions of poverty, lack of income and unemployment in Europe by adopting a public design approach. For being an action research project that intends to develop computer cooperative practices in contexts different from the workplace, and for its being backed by intellectual sensitivities that draw upon contemporary critical theory, Autonomous Marxism (henceforth, AM) in particular, PIE News can be an interesting case whereby to reflect upon how such theoretical inspirations benefit CSCW research.

Before discussing the contribution of AM, we shall point to the performative character of theoretical tools by drawing on suggestions from Science and Technology Studies (STS) and social theory. A similar understanding is in fact the most appropriate one to define the role of theory in PIE News.

The performative character of theories

Besides the descriptive, rhetorical, inferential and application power that Christine Halverson [6] attributes to theories, we suggest that theoretical perspectives are performative as John Law and John Urry [12] argue. This means that social science and its methods are productive in the sense that they help to

enact social worlds, rather than to simply describe it. A similar understanding of theories inevitably interrogates research projects and researchers about what kind of worlds they help to make. It therefore marks out a shift from empiricist realism (the assumption that there is a single reality 'out there' to be described given a context and purposes of the study) to ontological multiplicity [15], namely the understanding that reality is done and enacted by theoretical practices, rather than simply observed. Moreover, if social research enacts certain realities rather than others, then it should be taken into account the realities it contributes to build up. This is, in fact, a matter of "ontological politics" insofar as it calls into question the political and ethical character of social theories and methods (15).

These meta-theoretical assumptions inform the role that theories play in PIE News, an EU-funded project conceived as a design intervention emerging at the convergence of AM and recent developments in Participatory Design.

Computing, cooperation and the common

In claiming that CSCW did not emerge as a specialization of an established discipline and was not formed with a defined and generally agreed-to research program, Schmidt and Bannon clarify that such interdisciplinary research program "emerged and continually emerges as researchers engaged with the development of different technologies or working with different application domains realize that they in their own work are faced with related problems and then seek to explore and articulate these problems" (p. 347). In this respect, the development of internet-based platforms, like social networking sites, has shown how the capacity of coordinating with the

support of computing has extended its reach also outside the workplace [4]. This new role of computing in supporting coordinative practices in contexts different from the workplace implies new challenges for the field of CSCW, which go beyond the analysis of specific case studies.

Accordingly, we argue that today designers of digital technologies supporting cooperation may find themselves in need of reconsidering the relations between the socio-economic forms of work and the cooperative practices people engage with. In fact, many scholars in the social sciences have debated the forms of "free labor" [22] that digitally-mediated cooperative production has assumed. In the context of global value chains, that include mines, factories, and digital platforms [5], the last ones are particularly interesting in this paper. According to media scholar Josè van Dijck [2], social media platforms are changing over time to extract more and more economic value from social cooperation of unpaid subjects. Equally, platform capitalism is disrupting previously existing social arrangements, benefiting mainly capital accumulation [19]. Both are forms of what Harvey [9] called "accumulation by dispossession", in which capital appropriates the fruit of social cooperation generally autonomous from capital itself, if not social cooperation in itself as in the case of social media. We argue that a similar configuration poses a challenge for observers and designers of cooperative systems, that of reconsidering the socio-economic organization of cooperation as part of their agenda.

As the social sciences have helped to illuminate the process of commodification of computer supported cooperation, it is in the domain of critical theory that

designers can find the theoretical tools to question computer supported cooperation in the light of the actual socio-economic organization. This is because critical theories, forms of Marxism in particular, have always placed at the center of their analysis labor as social cooperation, contrasting it with capital as wealth accumulation. For Marxism, one of the main contradictions is exactly the one between the expansion of the cooperative capacities of social cooperation and the trials of capital to extract wealth from social cooperation itself [9]. In particular, the stream of Marxism known as Autonomous Marxism (AM) developed in the 1970s posing at the center of its analysis the autonomy of social cooperation, to which capital is reactive, framing labor and extracting value from it. Moreover, AM, through concepts like 'the multitude' [8], has integrated in its analysis post-structuralist accounts, like the ones of Foucault or Deleuze, and has expanded the focus from the industrial working class to whoever contribute to capital accumulation, in what can be defined as the 'life theory of value' [16].

In one of their most influential books, Hardt and Negri [7] have clarified what is the object of what Harvey has defined as "dispossession" [9], that is the ability of capital to extract value from social cooperation. The object of dispossession is what the autonomists define as "the common", the ensemble of the material and symbolic resources that favor social cooperation and that are, through different means, extracted by contemporary capitalism.

Similar concerns suggest the following question: how could a design process that frames social cooperation as its goal be defined, and how to deal with concepts as

wide as "the multitude" or to include the general processes of nurturing or dispossessing the common?

Historically, the design approach that has been more sensible to critical theory has been Scandinavian Participatory Design (PD) [20], that developed in the context of strong unionism in the workplace, with the aim to support the workers.

Recent developments in PD have extended its empirical settings beyond the workplace, toward a community-driven approach [3], that focuses on public formation [13], and that is able to promote the emergence of digital commons [21]. From this point of view, the growing attention in PD to the concept of "publics", as elaborated by Dewey [1] and discussed by Marres [14] in STS, looks like a promising elaboration. A public, for Dewey, is a group of people tied by concerns for the same issue and publics are not pre-existing the emergence of the issue itself. Therefore, what differentiates the reference to publics from the accent on communities is that publics are issue-driven [3] and constantly in formation during a design project [13].

Our theoretical elaboration promotes a dialogue between public design and AM, showing how a public design process potentially able to nurture the common can be analytically framed through three concurrent processes [21]. The first one, the articulation of matters of concern, is the process through which the "thingness" of a designed technology is kept open to scrutiny and controversy. The second one, the establishment of a digital commons, is what allows the definition of the institutional and legal framework for the collective management of a digital resource. The third one, recursive engagement, is the social process

through which singularities can be engaged and sustained in their participation to the collective management of a digital resource [21].

An agenda for the design of public cooperative systems?

The accent on public design as a design approach suggests that we can think at projects like PIE News as 'public cooperative system', in which cooperation nurturing the common is taking place within a public concerned with a specific issue and with a blurred relation with traditional forms of organization of labor, like companies or public administrations, or even communities characterized by tight bonds.

To frame a project in such a way, we have articulated the possibility to refer to the theoretical lenses of contemporary critical theory, especially AM, that regards the autonomy and growth of cooperative production as its main theoretical concept and political perspective. Moreover, as a consequence of the possibility to design technologies that extend beyond the workplace to acquire societal relevance, we have suggested referring to public design as a design approach that is issue-driven and that entails the process of public formation, in which public refers to a group of people concerned with a specific issue.

The PIE News project is a case of combination of AM theoretical influence and a public design approach. On one side, it leverages the idea that the multitude of the poor has a social priority on institutionalized power that tries to contain and discipline the poor initiatives [7]. On the other side, it promotes a design process that is able to intercept such initiatives and to sustain and support them, with the aim of public formation [21]. In

fact, the choice was to deal with the new poor as a group of people potentially able to turn into a public through the shared concerns on the improvement of their life conditions. Moreover, AM has always pointed to the distribution of wealth as a main topic of its theoretical and political action, and with PIE News the consortium chose to target the issues of poverty, income distribution, and employment, recognizing the centrality of digital technologies for contemporary political economy.

If we try to do the opposite, that is recognizing the centrality of political economy for the design and use of digital technologies, a set of research questions relevant to re-frame some basic questions in CSCW emerges. In particular, we refer here to the achievements of CSCW as summarized by Schmidt [17], and that we adapt in the form of questions crucial for those who plan research projects involving the design of public cooperative systems:

How does cooperative work and coordinative practices relate to the socio-economic organization of cooperation and society? What are the main coordinative artifacts and associated protocols? What the ordering systems at play? And how do cooperative work, coordinative practices, coordinative artifacts, and ordering systems act back on the socio-economic organization of cooperation and society as a whole?

Indeed, to reverse the commodification of cooperation in contemporary digital capitalism, we need new coordinative artifacts, associated protocols, or ordering systems able to exclude commodification in favor of the autonomy of cooperation itself.

Concluding remarks

In this paper, we have discussed how critical theory is influencing our work in the PIE News project. Our description is based on two concurrent assumptions: first, that theories make reality, not only describe it; second, that the relationship between social cooperation, digital technologies, and capital can be fruitfully read and rebuilt on the basis of contemporary critical theory. In particular, we have discussed how critical theory and forms of contemporary participatory design can be aligned in the light of contemporary digital capitalism. In conclusion, we have outlined a few questions for CSCW, showing how the achievements of the field so far can benefit from a renewed attention to political economy, in order to fit in the current social context in a progressive way.

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